

TRADE TURNOVER FOR HAZELNUTS: CURRENT SITUATION AND NEW DIGITAL OPPORTUNITIES**Gadashov A.,***Center for Analysis and Communication of Economic Reforms**Head of "Azexport" internet portal;**Doctoral student of the Agrarian Research Center***Iskandarli A.***Master's student of Baku State University***Abstract**

The article examines the current state of trade circulation of hazelnut products in the world and in Azerbaijan. The flow of import and export of hazelnut products in the countries of the world was touched upon. At the same time, the article provided information on the possibilities of using modern digital solutions in order to diversify the export geography of hazelnuts produced in Azerbaijan.

Keywords: hazel-nut, import, Azexport, import flow, export, export flow, market.

In 2020, fresh or dried, in-shell nuts and fibers were the world's 1310th most traded commodity, with a total trade of \$1.87 billion [5]. If we look at 2019, it can be noted that more than 90.0% of the worldwide production of hazelnuts was produced by Turkey (69.0%), Italy (8.8%), Azerbaijan (4.8%), the United States (3.5%), Chile (3.1 %) and China (2.6%) [1, p. 8].

During January-August 2022, fruit and vegetable products exported from Azerbaijan accounted for 93.2 percent of the group of agricultural products. During the corresponding period of 2022, the export of edible fruits and nuts increased by 25.1 percent to 227.7 million US dollars, and the export of vegetables amounted to 180.5 million US dollars [3].

The state has paid special attention to the cultivation of hazelnuts in Azerbaijan. Nut seedlings were distributed to entrepreneurs in the regions. An example of this is the distribution of hazelnut seedlings to citizens in 2019. As it can be seen, the increase of hazelnut orchards is one of the urgent issues in the interest of the state.

CURRENT SITUATION OF HAZELNUT IMPORT AND EXPORT IN ITALY:

One of the main economic sectors of Italy is agriculture. Italy is one of the largest agricultural producers and food processors in the European Union (EU). In the northern part of Italy, mainly grains, soy, meat and dairy products are produced, while in the south, fruits, vegetables, olive oil, wine and durum wheat are produced. Italian industry, as well as the food processing sector, is highly dependent on raw material imports. If we look at the Italian retail food market, we should note that this market is multifaceted. Also, most imported food products enter the Italian market through brokers or specialized traders [7].

One of the most common fruits in Italy is the hazelnut. The most popular hazelnut varieties are Hazelnut Giffoni IGP (Campania), Tonda Gentile Romana DOP (Lazio), Tonda Gentile Trilobata IGP (Piedmont) and Siciliana o Nostrale (Sicily) [4].

The Republic of Italy has a great role in the international economic relations of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Diplomatic relations between the two countries were established on May 8, 1992. The Italian embassy

was established in Azerbaijan in March 1997, and the Azerbaijani embassy in Italy in December 2003. Inter-parliamentary relations A working group on inter-parliamentary relations between Azerbaijan and Italy operates in the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Also, an Italian-Azerbaijani friendship group was established in the Italian Senate. Azerbaijan and Italy have mutually beneficial cooperation within the framework of a number of international organizations as well as at the level of their parliamentary assemblies, and it is considered appropriate to further deepen this cooperation in the future. There are close relations between our parliaments. It is gratifying that there are working groups of deputies on relations in both parliaments, and recent mutual visits make important contributions to these relations.

Relations between Italy and Azerbaijan are built on solid foundations. To date, 30 documents have been signed between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Italy. The documents signed between the two countries opened new opportunities for cooperation.

Azerbaijan-Italy business forum was held in Rome on February 21, 2020. During his speech at this forum, the Minister of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation of Italy noted that "Italy is considered the first trade partner of Azerbaijan. In less than ten years, our trade relations have increased to 70 percent. In the last ten years, Italy's imports from Azerbaijan amounted to 55.5 billion euros. Today, the Italian companies participating here operate in various fields - not only in the oil and gas field, but also in other fields. These companies are expected to support the development of our relations. The value of tenders won by Italian companies in Azerbaijan in the last 15 years is 7 billion euros. Our relations reaffirm our important strategic cooperation. Indeed, we express our great gratitude for the efforts made by the government of Azerbaijan in the field of economy, as well as in the direction of strengthening relations with businessmen. The government supports the legal system to protect the business environment as well as SMEs and other business people. More than 100 of our companies are currently operating in Azerbaijan. From design to tourism, from agricultural industry to

green technology, from transport to logistics, we operate in Azerbaijan. Of course, this is the result of the great support provided to our companies in Azerbaijan."

Italy is always of great interest as a country with a rich culture, a great state history, a strong economy, and a unique place in world politics. Azerbaijan also has a special interest in this country. Therefore, Italian literature, history and culture are followed with great interest in our country. There are many points where our interests coincide politically and economically. Italian businessmen and companies invest in the economy of Azerbaijan and closely participate in the exploitation of hydrocarbon resources of the Caspian Sea. We hope that Italy will support our country in the process of integration into European and Euro-Atlantic organizations, including strengthening relations with the European Union, as well as Azerbaijan's membership in World Trade Organizations, which are the main priorities of our country's foreign policy.

In 2021, the trade turnover between the two countries amounted to 4.5 billion US dollars, of which 95.65 percent of the trade turnover was the export of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the Republic of Italy. As a result of this, the foreign trade turnover of our country with Italy has a positive balance.

In 2021, the main exporters of hazelnuts in Italy are the first 5 countries [10]:

1. Germany 180.59 million US dollars (share of export value 51.56%)
2. Poland 45.32 million USD (share of export value 12.94%)
3. United Kingdom 43.62 million US dollars (12.45% share in export value)
4. France 40.75 million US dollars (share of export value 11.64%)
5. Spain 11.78 million US dollars (3.36% share in export value).

In that year, the first 5 countries distinguished themselves in the import of hazelnut products in Italy [11]:

1. Turkey 254.85 million US dollars (65.54% share in import value)
2. Chile 75.28 million USD (share of import value 19.36%)
3. Azerbaijan 28.19 million US dollars (7.25% share in import value)
4. Georgia 14.27 million US dollars (3.67% share in import value)
5. Luxembourg 5.72 million US dollars (1.47% share in import value).

Figure 1

CURRENT SITUATION OF HAZELNUT IMPORT AND EXPORT IN THE WORLD:

In 2020, edible nuts, fresh or dried, were the 993rd most traded commodity in the world, with a total trade of \$2.8 billion. Between 2019 and 2020, exports of edible, fresh or dried hazelnuts increased by 0.68 percent, from \$2.78 billion to \$2.8 billion. Hazelnuts are ranked

4710th in the Product Complexity Index [6]. The Product Complexity Index is based on two key concepts. These are the criteria of diversity and ubiquity.

It should be noted that 80 percent of the world hazelnut trade is in Europe, and this product is bought by enterprises in Europe. It is mostly used in the preparation of confectionery products.

Global Hazelnut Market : Market Share in %, Region, 2021

Figure 2. Global Hazelnut Market: Percentage Market Share, Region, 2021

In 2021, the first 5 countries were distinguished in the export of hazelnuts: Turkey 1.29 billion US dollars (share of export value 58.29%), Italy 350.23 million US dollars (share of export value 15.79%), Chile 154.17 million US dollars (share of export value 6.95%), Azerbaijan 109.47 million US dollars (share of export value 4.93%), Georgia 95.38 million US dollars (share of export value 4.3%) [12].

In 2021, the largest export flow was from Turkey to Italy (export value 443.18 million USD) [12].

Figure 3. Export flows for 2021 [12].

According to the import of hazelnuts, the first 5 countries in the world distinguished themselves in 2021: Germany 582.45 million US dollars (share of import value 28.54%), Italy 388.86 million US dollars (share of import value 19.05%), France 166.93 million US dollars (share of import value 8.18%), Russia 77.34

million US dollars (share of import value 3.79%), Canada 71.66 million US dollars (share of import value 3.51%) [13].

In 2021, the largest import flow was from Germany to Turkey (export value 324.92 million US dollars) [13].

Figure 4. Import flows for 2021 [13].

CURRENT SITUATION OF HAZELNUT EXPORT IN AZERBAIJAN AND CHALLENGES:

In 2020, the area of hazelnut orchards in our country was 79.6 thousand hectares. In that year, the area of hazelnut orchards increased by 2.4 times compared to 2015, and by 0.1 percent compared to 2019 [1, p.3]. Also, in the same year, the export of shelled hazelnuts in our country increased by 66.3 percent compared to the previous year, while the shelled (kernel) export decreased by 18.9 percent. Thus, 94.6 percent of the total hazelnut exports were hazelnut kernels, and 5.4 percent were hazelnuts in shell [1, p.7].

Our country is the main importer of hazelnut products. Thus, in 2021, the value of hazelnuts imported by

our country was 696.40 thousand US dollars (its share in the import value was 98.59%). For that year, after our country, 4 countries stood out in the main import of hazelnuts [9]:

1. Georgia 6 thousand US dollars (0.85% share in import value)
2. Italy 2.40 thousand US dollars (share of import value 0.34%)
3. Turkey 1.25 thousand US dollars (0.18% share in import value)
4. Luxembourg 245 USD (0.03% share of import value).

Figure 5. Trends of countries that are the main hazelnut importers for Azerbaijan [9].

Among the hazelnut exporting regions in our country, Khachmaz and Guba stand out, and 20-25 percent of the hazelnut export falls to these regions. Zagatala (31.1%), Balaken (12.6%), Gabala (12.0%), Sheki (8.1%), Gakh (6.4%) and Gusar (6.4%) regions accounted for 89.6 percent of hazelnut production in 2020.

According to the statistical data of 2021, our country was in the 4th place after Chile in terms of the export of hazelnuts in the world in that year. In that year, hazelnuts worth 109.47 million US dollars were exported from the Republic of Azerbaijan [8].

In 2021, our country's main exporter of hazelnuts was Russia. In that year, the first 5 countries were distinguished by the export of hazelnuts from our country [8]:

1. Russia 47.24 million US dollars (its share in the export value is 43.15%).
2. Italy 34.73 million US dollars (share of export value 31.73%)
3. Germany 16.99 million US dollars (share of export value 15.52%)
4. Kazakhstan 2.78 million US dollars (2.54% share in export value)
5. Luxembourg 1.40 million US dollars (1.28% share in export value).

The emergence of modern digital technologies has also affected trade relations. Thus, the use of digital capabilities makes it easier to export products to foreign markets. As an example, we can mention "Aznut" company. In 2019, the products of "Aznut" company rose to the "Best Seller" category among nut products on the world's largest sales platform, "Amazon". This company buys hazelnuts from the Republic of Azerbaijan. "Aznut" company has FDA, USDA, Non-GMO and Kosher certificates [2].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Currently, there are some difficulties in the export of hazelnuts. The reason for this is the lack of education of farmers, misunderstandings between farmers and producers, etc. One of the other main reasons is that the demand for hazelnuts in the Arab countries is not high, so the sales are weak. Therefore, the main export market is Europe. Things that can be done in this area are as follows:

1. Integration into Azexport.az portal. The Azexport portal was created on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated September 21, 2016 "On the creation of a unified database of goods produced in the Republic of Azerbaijan". Azexport provides support to exporting entrepreneurs in the field of transportation, payment and certification, as well as logistics in order to improve the business environment in the country. The portal increases access to the world market of products produced in Azerbaijan and expands their sales scope. Thus, the Azexport portal is integrated into more than 15 portals with a wide audience, such as Amazon.com, "alibaba.com", "ebay", "all.biz", "Go4worldbusiness.com". In this way, entrepreneurs can enter international markets more easily by using the digital opportunities provided by the portal. From January 2016 to November 2022, the Portal accepted more than \$ 3 billion in export orders from 145 countries of the world and submitted them to local entrepreneurs.

2. "Tradeatlas.com" , "Trademap.com". Through these sites, the opportunities for buyers to enter the markets are increasing, and as a result, the access to potential customers is increasing. Entrepreneurs can reach real buyers using these modern solutions.

3. Increasing knowledge of electronic commerce (e-commerce) of entrepreneurs. E-commerce offers a number of advantages to entrepreneurs. So low prices, fast delivery, easy research and comparison, no utility and rent fees, etc. At the same time, e-commerce opportunities provide them with conditions for easier access to international markets. As a result, entrepreneurs began to show more interest in this field. Thus, it can be considered appropriate to pay more attention to teaching relevant knowledge and skills to entrepreneurs in this field.

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MANAGEMENT OF BANK RISKS IN FINANCIAL MARKETS AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Since the crises experienced in the financial markets in recent years have brought the view to the fore that the financial sectors of developed and developing countries should be structured in a healthy way. The main elements of the new approach are creating a stable operating environment, developing financial markets, ensuring transparency, strengthening the national and international financial sector, and making joint efforts to prevent international financial crises. Within the scope of strengthening the national financial system, restructuring of banks, which traditionally constitute the most important institutions of the financial system in developing countries, has gained importance.

Risk management is of great importance for banks, which are the heart of financial markets. In order to increase their profitability, banks need to produce effective risk management systems that can meet the ever-increasing and changing demands of the market by constantly associating the capital-return-risk trio with each other. The purpose of risk management is to measure in advance the magnitude of losses that the markets may face in extraordinary situations while they are enduring their activities in order to be prepared for the extraordinary situations.

In this article, the purpose and importance of risk management in bank risks are defined and the measurement and management techniques of these risks are assessed. As such, after defining the concept of risks, the risks arising from the banking sector and the management methods of these risks are emphasized.

Keywords: Banking Sector, Bank risks, Risk Management

Review of the Risks Encountered in the Banking Sector

While the risks that banks are exposed to has a direct effect on their profitability, at the same time, they have an indirect effect on their capital adequacy and market shares. Effective management of such risks would allow to increase the profitability. If the bank complements a part of its profit to its capital, it will be able to increase its market share by strengthening its financial structure. The purpose of risk management is not to prevent the bank from taking risks. On the contrary, it is to increase profitability and financial performance by reducing the risks that the bank may face and preventing losses and increasing the extent of activities.

Bessis and Schroeck interpret the risks in banking as negative effects on those obtained from different impressions [3; 13]. According to Cade, risks in banking refer to the difference between the return of the banking system and the expected present value of the cash flows of these transactions [8]. From the perspective of bank, the risk is the condition where the expected income is lower than the expected return.

Financial risks are articulated as the probability of loss resulting from not achieving a financial target. Risk reflects uncertainty about exchange rates, interest rates, commodity prices, stock prices, credit quality, liquidity and an organization's access to finance. Financial risks are not independent of each other. For example, exchange rates and interest rates are often strongly linked. As such, this link should be taken into account when designing risk management models by managers. This link should be taken into account when designing risk management models by managers [26, pp. 1-30].

In general, banking activities pose many unique risks. These risks are risks such as a bank's loans, liquidity, trade, revenues and costs, earnings and solvency. The types of risks encountered by banks can be conveyed as interest rate risk, country risk, market risk, currency risk, liquidity risk, credit risk, management risk, operational risk, legal risk, reputation risk and bankruptcy risk.

Interest Rate Risk: it is the price that determines the balance of supply and demand in the economy. For